

DESIGN PRINCIPLES FOR SPATIALLY REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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The expediency of spatial reinforcement is defined by the capability of tailoring the properties of a composite in all directions of a material macrovolume and localizing the fracture within a small material volume composed of only one or several unit cells. Depending on the way of spatial bonds formation, the fiber composites with spatial fiber orientation can be subdivided into several groups. The spatial bonds can be formed by a system of one, two, three and four filaments in Cartesian and polar coordinate systems. The attempts of passing over to multidirectional schemes of reinforcement are also known. To spatially reinforced materials belong also the materials, the spatial bonds in which are formed in the process of whiskerization. The elastic and strength properties of composites in the directions of fiber orientation are practically proportional to the volume fraction of fibers. The way of formation and number of spatial bonds impose restrictions on the magnitudes of reinforcement coefficients.

An urgent task is to develop the material having as uniform elastic and strength properties as possible in all directions at a minimum number of fiber orientations and highest magnitude of the coefficient of fiber volume fraction. It will be shown that the 4-D composite reinforced by a spatial system of four filaments fully satisfies this requirement. The analysis of the vector relation for fiber orientations of the material, with the conditions of fiber contact taken into account, has shown [1] that the maximum magnitude of coefficients of fiber volume fraction for fibers with circular cross section amounts to 0.68, whereas for hexahedral fibers - to 0.75. In these cases, the reinforcement directions coincide with mutual orientation of the main diagonals of a cube. In the case of curved fibers, the mutual interlooping of different-direction fiber families occurs at fairly high ultimate magnitude of the coefficient of fiber volume fraction, while weaving technology poses certain difficulties. The increase in the number of directions of spatial reinforcement by straight fibers is accompanied by the decrease in the coefficient of fiber volume fraction. In certain cases of reinforcing by straight fibers with various-diameter circular section, the coefficient of fiber volume fraction amounts to 0.49...0.65 for six directions parallel to the main diagonals of a cube and diagonals on a cube face. The diameters of fibers being equal, the maximum magnitude of coefficient of fiber volume fraction does not exceed 0.54 for five of the indicated directions.

To quantitatively evaluate the elastic and thermo-physical behavior of spatially reinforced materials, the theory of reinforced media has undergone its further elaboration. The effective constants are being calculated from approximate models. The deformation models for all material groups are based on the following procedure: characteristic repeating structural units are identified, their properties assessed from the properties of constituent materials, i.e. the fiber and the matrix, and "summation" of the elements as regards their joint functioning in the material. To determine the characteristics of the structural element

the analytical results of the theory of reinforced media have been employed, which are well developed and approbated for the case of a monotropic unidirectional material. Introduction of a modified matrix constitutes an exception in this stage; in the case of eliminating the fibers in one direction by the technique of energy smoothing, the modified matrix is considered to be monotropic, whereas upon spreading of the fiber properties in two orthogonal directions, it becomes orthotropic.

In the materials formed of a system of two and three filaments, the repeating structural element is identified as a layer. This procedure has been prompted by the specific features of the spatial material structure itself. The layer coupling is defined from the condition of joint deformation of layers. It should be noted that division of the 2-D material into layers is made parallel to the plane of warp fiber curvature. In this case the structural elements are represented by layers parallel to one another, comprising parts of curved fiber arcs being out of phase or, in a particular case, opposite in phase.

For materials formed of a system of one, four and n filaments, identification of cylindrical structural elements with a rectilinear or curvilinear axis is more visual. An approximate model of joint deformation of such elements takes into account the diverse orientation in respect to the loading direction and presupposes equal averaged deformation for all elements in the representative volume. The strain tensor is specified as invariant over the entire material volume. The effective constants for the spatially reinforced composite, represented by components of stiffness matrix B_{ij} ($i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 6$), are found by averaging of the respective components of stiffness matrix for structural elements (B_{ij}^0) with weight coefficients, corresponding to relative fiber volume fraction in a structural element, the elements being oriented in the material by means of two Euler angles. The analogous approach was extended to calculations of effective coefficients of linear thermal expansion α . As a result from the system of equations

$$B_{ij} \alpha_j = B_{ij}^0 \alpha_j^0 ; \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 6 \quad (1)$$

the effective value of α_j is being found. The right-hand part of (1) represents the magnitude of thermal stress in a closed undeformed material volume upon cooling by 1°C . The vector α^0 for a structural element in the system of material axes is represented by the components α_j^0 . The components can be either specified or calculated, proceeding from the fiber and matrix properties /2/. The accuracy of the approach based on the averaging of stiffness components has already been discussed in /1/. It should be added that analogous averaging of the components of compliance matrix for a structural element in a multi-directional material yields the magnitudes of effective elastic constants and α , which differ practically inessentially from the previous constants. In more refined versions, the components of stress-strain state in a structural element of the spatial material model were calculated by Pagano in accordance with the three-phase cylindrical model /4/, Takao and Chou in terms of the principle of Eshelby's equivalent inclusions /3/. Their averaging in determination of the effective constants for a spatially reinforced material, as shown by the analysis, does not introduce essential correction into the results of calculations according to the relationships proposed here. It follows from the fact that Pagano's model /4/ employs the condition of invariability of strain tensor for all structural elements. The difference in the results obtained consists only in coincidence of uniform stress field in the representative structural element and its averaged expression in accordance with the three-phase model—the fiber, the coating and the matrix. The stress fluctuations of such kind

are treated in /3/. The choice of the structural element as a layer or a unidirectional material predetermines the degree of freedom for deformability in "constructing" of the material. The transverse stresses in layers being equal, the transverse deformations can possibly differ. For a unidirectional element of a multi-directional material the Reiss and Foyt conditions for structural elements are mutually exclusive; their joint use is impossible. One should expect the highest error for the materials whose properties of structural elements differ greatly.

The most representative is the tailoring of effective composite properties in terms of the fiber orientation angle, stiffness and fiber volume fraction in the materials reinforced by a system of n filaments. Due to the fact that for a majority of these materials the elements of structural symmetry are characteristic, it is enough to indicate such a parameter which would allow to show the variance of properties with continuously varying spatial structure from a unidirectional structure to a planar one. The solid angle was selected as such a parameter in unfolding the "umbrella" of reinforcement orientations. Restricting oneself to four directions, ensuring dense fiber packing at n^3 , let us determine these directions along the diagonals of a perfect parallelepiped. Upon changing its height, all the spectrum of spatial structures can be surveyed.

The analysis of changes of elastic moduli of the 4-D composite has shown that in the case of fiber orientation along the diagonals of a cube Young's modulus of the material reinforced by high-modulus fibers is less than its shear modulus. This case corresponds to the cubic symmetry of elastic properties. Young's modulus of this material reaches its highest value along each of the four reinforcement paths:

$$E^{\max} = \frac{3E'}{4 - \frac{E'}{E_1}}, \quad E' = \frac{4G_{12}}{1 + 2G_{12}(1 - \nu_{21})/E_1} \quad (2)$$

The second formula of (2) allows one to calculate Young's modulus at 45° to the principal axes of elastic symmetry; E_1 , G_{12} , ν_{21} are Young's modulus, shear modulus and Poisson's ratio, respectively, in the principal axes of elastic symmetry.

The analysis has shown that the volume thermal strain $e^T = (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3) \cdot 10^6$ of the 4-D composite reinforced along the cubic diagonals is minimum among all spatial and planar reinforcement structures. For evaluation of α_T - value of an orthogonally reinforced 3-D composite and 4-D composite reinforced along the diagonals of a cube the following formula was obtained:

$$\alpha = \frac{n^0 \alpha_{11}^0 + \alpha_1^0}{n^0 + 1}, \quad n^0 = \frac{E_1^0}{E_2^0} \cdot \frac{1 - \nu_{23}^0 + 2 \nu_{12}^0}{2(1 + \nu_{21}^0)} \quad (3)$$

where the constants of a unidirectional structural element bear a superscript "0". The 3-D and 4-D composites are isotropic upon thermal expansion. The analysis has shown that, if a spatially reinforced material possesses symmetry of elastic properties no less than cubic one, then, provided the properties of material constituents and magnitudes of coefficients of fiber volume fraction are equal, α will be calculated in accordance with the formula (3).

The deformation and strength properties and α of the 4-D carbon-carbon composite with fibers aligned along the diagonals of a cube show a num-

ber of peculiarities. The effective value of α_T is by an order of magnitude lower than that of the polymeric-matrix-based composite. This is accounted for by comparatively low α_T values of carbon matrix and its anisotropy. α of carbon-carbon composite fluctuates around zero and, in some cases, turns out to be negative /5/. In strength testing of carbon-carbon composites the ultimate loads depend on the type of loading. In tension and torsion tests mainly fiber breakage occurs, whereas in compression - matrix cracking and delamination. In the tests indicated, we failed to observe brittle fracture of these materials due to gradual fiber delamination and matrix microcracking.

4-D composites...And what is the next step? Based on an analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of the realized structural schemes, the expediency of multi-directional reinforcement of higher order than 4-D seems to be problematic. The possible merits in specific areas of application do not compensate for essential technological difficulties in the process of tailoring of the isotropic properties of fiber composites /6/.

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